

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

UNDERSTANDING CNT DISPERSION IN POLYMER PRECURSOR SOLUTIONS AND PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES FROM THE ATOMIC SCALE

Hendrik Heinz – University of Colorado at Boulder

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Carbon Nanofiber Composites: Ultrastrong and Lightweight

Panels

Sheets

Yarns

Fibers

Lift-off cost per pound
\$1m for Mars, \$10k
for moon mission

STRI
(11 Inst/
19 Pls)

- High strength and low weight (density) are essential for air and space vehicles
- Carbon nanofibers and composites exceed modulus and strength of alloys and far exceed specific strength/modulus
- Near-term carbon nanofiber goals: 400 GPa modulus, 8 GPa strength

New Models for Graphitic/Layered Materials on the Nanoscale

- Poor reproduction of stacking/mechanics and interfacial properties by existing models
- Include of **π - π stacking and cation- π interactions** using **virtual electrons**

Li/Na/K⁺-benzene (kcal/mol)

Expt: **-38/-27/-19**

IFF: **-35/-29/-17**
<10% error

ReaxFF, CHARMM:
-1/-1/-1 kcal/mol
>1000% error

Pramanik et al. ACS Nano 2017, 11, 12805. Gissinger et al. ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces 2018, 10, 1017.

Expt vs model (force field)	Graphite density (g/cm ³)	Surface energy (mJ/m ²)	Hydration energy (mJ/m ²)	Contact angle – water (°)	Bulk mod. (GPa)
Expt.	2.25	186±5	-53±3	60±5	34
PCFF-IFF (new model)	2.21	186±3	-55±3	65±5	32
PCFF	2.26	167	+49	0	NA
CVFF	2.12	322	-25	0	NA
CHARMM36	2.39	143	-78	30	NA

Polyacrylonitrile crystallinity + CNT type = Composites of tailored inclusion energy, glass transition, and shear strength

CNT Dispersion in Solvents and Polymer Solutions

Binary systems:
CNTs + solvent

Ternary systems:
CNTs + polymers + solvent

CNT Dispersion in Solvents

PAN and PMMA + CNTs in DMSO

#ICCM22

CNT Dispersion in Polymer Solutions

C e O N S H

CNT Dispersion in MD Simulations vs Solubility Parameters

- Polymer adsorption on CNTs depends on solvent and polymer, better for PMMA vs PAN
- Better adsorption and dispersion in DMSO vs DMF, DMAc

- Range of available Hansen solubility parameters often large - hard to make quantitative statements
- New Hansen solubility parameters for SWCNTs and MWCNTs derived
- Simulations capture specifics better but take longer

compd	s parameter δ_T^b	δ_D	δ_P	δ_H	R_0^c	RED ^d
SWCNT (est) ^a	19.4 ± 0.7	18.5 ± 0.5	5 ± 2	3 ± 2		
MWCNT (est) ^a	19.9 ± 0.7	19.0 ± 0.5	5 ± 2	3 ± 2		
DMAc	22.7	16.8	11.5	10.2		0.42 (PMMA) 0.59 (PAN)
PMMA	22.7 (18–23)	18.6 (16–19)	10.5 (6.5–10.5)	7.5 (5.4–7.5)	11.0 (8.6–11)	
DMF	24.8	17.4	13.7	11.3		0.50 (PMMA) 0.49 (PAN)
PAN	25.3 (21–26)	18.2 (15–21)	16.2 (13–16)	6.8 (6.8–8)	10.9 (8–13)	
DMSO	26.7	18.4	16.4	10.2		0.63 (PMMA) 0.31 (PAN)

Pramanik, HH et al. ACS Nano 2017, 11, 12805.

CNT-PAN Interactions in Dilute Solution 1 wt% – Random Interactions

T = 25 °C

C e O N S H

T = 75 °C

CNT-PAN Interactions in Gel State 10 wt% – Random Interactions and More Surface Contact

4D Perspectives for PAN/CNT Interactions in DMAc (50 ns)

T = 25 °C

T = 75 °C

Binding Mechanisms and Conformation Characteristics

- PAN matching to surface pattern of carbon atoms on the CNT often seen
- Parallel orientation of CN groups common
- High concentration equalizes polymer conformations/influence of temperature

CNT/PAN Composite Models

Kumar, Heinz, et al.
ACS Appl. Mater.
Interfaces 2018, 10,
1017.

Glass Transition Temperature and Interfacial Ordering in PAN/CNT Composites

Below T_g chain rotation near surface is hindered

- Bond and pairwise nonbond energy indicate molecular ordering of PAN near the CNT surface

Bond energy (75% cryst.)

Pairwise energy

4 nm

- Correlation with graphitization extent in carbon nanofiber possible (TEM data)

- T_g increases with CNT/polymer interfacial area, i.e., volume fraction (unless bundled), not with CNT size

- T_g in high accuracy (± 5 K vs ± 20 K with older FFs)

Computed Interfacial Shear Strength in PAN/CNT Composites

Typical measurements for as-spun PAN/CNT fibers ~13 MPa

- Computed interfacial shear strengths agree well with measurements
- Higher values for SWCNTs and at least 50% pre-oriented PAN expected
- Nanoscale domain-macroscopic relationships for FE/DE models can be derived

Reaction Modelling - 10^7 Times Faster and Close to DFT

Collapsed CNT geometrical comparison

$$\Delta E = E_{\text{flat}} - E_{\text{open}}$$

Method	Threshold Diameter (nm)
DFT-D2	5.1
ReaxFF C-2013	3.5
PCFF-IFF	4.3
OPLS	6.2

Energy comparison of collapsed CNT

Comparison IFF/ReaxFF, Adri van Duin Penn State U

- ❑ PCFF-IFF has reasonable proximity to DFT-D2 data
- ❑ Transition from open to flat configurations are tabulated
- ❑ Reaxff C-2013* fails to predict the curved sites of the CNTs

EM, ReaxFF 2013

Reaxff to PCFF-IFF* model

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

*Reference: Dharmawardhana CC, Kanhaiya K, Lin TJ, Garley A, Knecht MR, Zhou J, Miao J, **heinz H.** Reliable computational design of biological-inorganic materials to the large nanometer scale using Interface-FF. Molecular Simulation. 2017 Nov 2;43(13-16):1394-405.

#ICCM22

Summary and Outlook

- Realistic insights at the small nanometers scaler are feasible by modeling and simulation
- Several direct correlations with macroscale properties
- Cross-scale simulations could predict properties up to the micron scale in high reliability

Acknowledgements

Dr. Chandrani Pramanik, CU
 Jacob Gissinger, CU
 Samuel Hoff, CU
 Amanda Garley, CU
 Satish Kumar, Georgia Tech
 Amir Davijani, Georgia Tech

Dhriti Nepal, AFRL
 Behzad Damirchi, Penn State U
 Adri van Duin, Penn State U
 Matthew Radue, Michigan Tech
 Gregory Odegard, Michigan Tech

CORNING

NATIONAL LABORATORY

THANK YOU

For Your Attention